

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Research on factors affecting the living and learning habits of gen Z generation: The case of students of the school of economics - Hanoi university of industry

Thuy Thi Nguyen *, Tuyet Thi Duong, Trang Huyen Thi Hoang, Ha Van Thi Nguyen and Ha Thu Thi Mai

Faculty of Management, School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry

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Abstract

This study aims to identify and analyze the factors affecting the living and learning habits of Gen Z, with the survey subjects being students of the School of Economics – Hanoi University of Industry. Through quantitative research methods combined with qualitative, data were collected from 401 students using survey questionnaires and group interviews. The results of the analysis show that the main factors affecting Gen Z's living and learning habits include: learning environment, friends around them, lecturers, family – society, the influence of technology and their own cognitive methods. In particular, methods and self-awareness have the strongest impact on the organization of personal activities and learning efficiency of Gen Z. Next is the influence of technology. The study also showed differences in habits between groups of students by school year and gender. From the results achieved, the article proposes a number of solutions to help Gen Z students form living and learning habits.

Keywords: Gen Z generation; Living habits; Study habits; Students; Hanoi University of Industry

1. Introduction

In the context of increasingly deep digital transformation and globalization, the Gen Z generation – a group of people born between the late 1990s and early 2010s – is becoming the main learning and labor force in society. Unlike previous generations, Gen Z has matured in a thriving technology environment, with the ubiquitous presence of the internet, smartphones, and social networks. These factors not only change the way they access information, but also profoundly affect their living and study habits. In Vietnam, Gen Z currently accounts for a large proportion of universities and colleges, especially among students studying at higher education institutions. Understanding the factors affecting the living and learning habits of Gen Z not only helps schools, lecturers and parents better understand the characteristics of this generation, but also creates a basis for building appropriate educational policies and methods, improve training efficiency. Although there have been many studies in the world and in Vietnam mentioning the relationship between technology, social networks, educational environment and student learning behavior, a comprehensive and systematic analysis of factors affecting Gen Z's living and learning habits in a specific context is still limited. Therefore, this study was conducted to identify and evaluate the factors affecting the living and learning habits of Gen Z students, with the survey subjects being students of the School of Economics – Hanoi University of Industry. Theoretical basis and research methods.

1.1. Theoretical basis

Research by the Pew Research Center (2018) has determined that the popularity of social media platforms among young people, especially YouTube, Instagram, and Snapchat. The results show that 95% of teens own smartphones, and 45% of them use the internet almost constantly.

* Corresponding author: Nguyen Thi Thuy

Jean Twenge (2017) in his book "iGen" analyzed the impact of family, education, and technology on the behavior and lifestyle habits of Gen Z. Twenge points out that Gen Z, or iGen, is the first generation to grow up entirely in the digital age, with the constant presence of smartphones and social networks.

The results of a study by Ralph B. McNeal Jr. (2014) with the aim of analyzing the relationship between parental involvement and student learning achievement, and examining the role of learning attitudes and behaviors show that parental involvement can be divided into two main categories: parent-child involvement, including discussion and monitoring of learning, and parent-school involvement, such as educational support and participation in parent-teacher organizations.

The results of a study by Vu Van Tuan et al. (2021) on "The Impact of Social Networking Sites on Study Habits and Interpersonal Relationships among Vietnamese Students" on the analysis of the influence of social networks on the study habits and social relationships of Vietnamese students have shown that the use of social networks can lead to a decrease in concentration in studying, negatively impact academic outcomes and change the way students interact socially.

The study "Family - An important factor in moral education for students and students" by Tran Van Phuc and Nguyen Kim Tuyen (2014) emphasizes the essential role of the family in the formation and development of personality, as well as the study habits of students and students.

Research on factors affecting Gen Z's living and learning habits has become an important topic in research on education and society. Domestic and international studies have proven that factors such as technology, social networks, the environment and family have had a profound influence on living habits, thereby affecting the learning outcomes of Gen Z.

1.2. Research hypothesis

- Hypothesis 1: The learning environment has a positive effect on the living and learning habits of Gen Z
- Hypothesis 2: Friends around you have a positive influence on the living and learning habits of Gen Z
- Hypothesis 3: Lecturers have a positive influence on the living and learning habits of Gen Z
- Hypothesis 4: Family – society has a positive influence on the living and learning habits of Gen Z
- Hypothesis 5: Self-awareness has a positive effect on Gen Z's living and learning habits.
- Hypothesis 6: Learning methods have a positive effect on the living and learning habits of Gen Z
- Hypothesis 7: Technology has a negative impact on Gen Z's living and learning habits

1.3. Recommended research model:

Based on the theory and results of the process of conducting an overview of domestic and foreign studies, the team proposed a research model on factors affecting the living and learning habits of Generation Z: The case of students of the School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry with 7 influencing factors including: (1) Learning environment; (2) Friends around; (3) Lecturers; (4) Family – society; (5) Self-awareness; (6) Learning methods; (7) Technology. These factors are synthesized, building a research model and hypotheses as below:

Source: Recommended authors

Figure 1 Research model

2. Data and research methodology

The main method for collecting survey data on a large scale using questionnaires. During a period of 6 months (from 9/2024 to 3/2025), the authors sent questionnaires to first-year, 2nd, 3rd-year students, 4th-year students, students who are doing internships, students who have completed internships and are participating in studying at the School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry. This is a group of students who have been studying and researching at the School of Economics, Hanoi University of Industry. Receipts are cleaned and invalid votes are removed. The total number of votes after cleaning and putting into the data analysis was 401 votes. The analytical techniques used in this report include: Cronbach's Alpha scale validation, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), multiple regression analysis. The software used in the analysis is SPSS 26.

3. Result and discussion

3.1. EFA Discovery Factor Analysis

3.1.1. For independent variables

The authors conducted an exploratory factor analysis of EFA to reduce the observed variables that correlate with each other into a smaller set and the synthetic variables were more meaningful but still ensured the information content of the original data set; at the same time, eliminate interfering variables, which are not suitable for the research model. Barlett test results and KMO index = 0.866; SIG <0.05 proves that the factor analysis model proposed by the authors is appropriate and the observed variables are closely correlated with each other.

Table 1 KMO test results of independent variables

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.866
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	8078.799
	df	351
	Sig.	<.001

(Source: SPSS data running results)

Next is the analysis of the rotation matrix, after the process of research, verification and elimination of inappropriate variables, the initial rotation matrix with 7 elements has been adjusted, combining elements with similarities to ensure a more reasonable research model. According to Hair & et al. (2009), factors with a load factor greater than 0.5 are satisfactory, and in the final result table, many of the observed variables have a high load factor above ± 0.7 , demonstrating very good statistical significance. The final results of the factor analysis show 5 main groups of factors, which are presented in the table below:

Table 2 Matrix rotates the factors of the independent variable

Rotated Component Matrix ^a					
	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
NT3	0.724				
NT1	0.722				
PP1	0.721				
PP3	0.708				
NT4	0.697				
PP2	0.696				
NT2	0.678				
PP4	0.574				
MT2		0.834			
BB2		0.828			
GDXH4		0.536			
GDXH3		0.510			
MT4		0.822			
BB4		0.818			
GDXH2		0.601			
CN3			0.849		
CN1			0.791		
CN2			0.789		
CN4			0.714		
GV1				0.809	
GV3				0.789	
GV2				0.665	
MT3					0.892
BB3					0.803
MT1					0.919
BB1					0.810

(Source: SPSS data running results)

3.1.2. For dependent variables

Table 3 KMO test results of dependent variables

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.788
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	599.035
	df	6
	Sig.	<.001

(Source: SPSS data running results)

The results of the factor analysis show that the KMO index is $0.788 > 0.5$, which proves that the data used for factor analysis is completely appropriate.

Barlett's test results with Sig significance level = $0.000 < 0.05$ observed variables are not correlated with each other in the whole, variables are correlated with each other and meet the conditions for factor analysis

Table 4 Results of extractive variance analysis of dependent variables

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.646	66.154	66.154	2.646	66.154	66.154
2	0.597	14.914	81.068			
3	0.432	10.797	91.864			
4	0.325	8.136	100.000			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						

(Source: SPSS data running results)

Perform factor analysis by Principal components with Varimax rotation. The results show that the total value of the extracted variance = $66.154\% > 50\%$, then it can be said that this factor explains 66.154% of the variability of the data.

Table 5 Component matrix of dependent variables

Component Matrix^a	
	Component
	1
TQ4	0.847
TQ2	0.836
TQ1	0.831
TQ3	0.735
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.	
a. 1 components extracted.	

(Source: SPSS data running results)

3.2. Pearson Correlation Analysis

To perform a polyupile linear regression analysis, we need to consider the correlation between independent and dependent variables and between independent variables. Correlation analysis is a measure of the strength/weakness of the association between the research variables in the model expressed by the Pearson coefficient. From the results of the correlation analysis coefficient, the values show that the variables are correlated with each other, specifically shown in the table below:

Table 6 Correlation matrix between factors

Correlations		Study and living habits	Perceptions and Methods	Technology	Lecturer	Environment and friends	Family and Society
Study and living habits	Pearson Correlation	1	0.693**	0.410**	0.439**	0.383**	0.594**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	401	401	401	401	401	401
Perceptions and Methods	Pearson Correlation	0.693**	1	0.294**	0.458**	0.559**	0.731**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	401	401	401	401	401	401
Technology	Pearson Correlation	0.410**	0.294**	1	0.204**	0.191**	0.232**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	401	401	401	401	401	401
Lecturer	Pearson Correlation	0.439**	0.458**	0.204**	1	0.343**	0.397**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	401	401	401	401	401	401
Environment and friends	Pearson Correlation	0.383**	0.559**	0.191**	0.343**	1	0.646**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	401	401	401	401	401	401
Family and Society	Pearson Correlation	0.594**	0.731**	0.232**	0.397**	0.646**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	401	401	401	401	401	401

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

(Source: SPSS data running results)

Based on the correlations table provided, we can comment as follows: The results of the Pearson correlation analysis show that all independent factors have a relationship with study and living habits at a meaningful level of 0.01 ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that these factors have a significant influence on students' study habits. In particular, cognition and learning methods had the highest correlation with study and living habits ($r = 0.693$), indicating that learning methods and personal cognition play an important role in the formation of learning habits.

In addition, family and society ($r = 0.594$), faculty ($r = 0.439$), environment and friends ($r = 0.383$), and technology ($r = 0.410$) also had a significant correlation with study habits, proving that these factors all impact how students organize and maintain their study habits. Notably, the relationship between cognition and learning methods with family and society has a fairly high correlation coefficient ($r = 0.731$), indicating that the family environment has a great influence on how students receive and develop learning methods.

In addition, independent factors are also correlated with each other, such as the association between environment and friends with cognition and learning methods ($r = 0.559$), suggesting that a good friend environment can help students improve their cognition and learning methods. The correlation between technology and cognition and learning methods ($r = 0.294$) also suggests that the use of technology may support students' learning but the impact is not so strong.

3.3. Results of Regression Analysis

In order to identify, measure and evaluate the influence of factors on the learning habits of Gen Z in the School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry, the authors used the multiplex linear regression method to analyze the impact of independent variables (05 variables) obtained from the exploratory factor analysis above to the depend.

Table 7 Linear regression model synthesis results

Model Summary^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.748 ^a	0.559	0.554	0.51690	1.652
a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceptions and Learning Methods, Technology, Family and Society, Environment and Friends, Lecturers					
b. Dependent Variable: Study and living habits					

(Source: SPSS data running results)

- The R2 value corrected by 0.554 shows that the independent variable introduced into the regression run affects 55.4% of the change of the dependent variable, the remaining 45.3 is due to extra-model variables and random errors.

- The Durbin - Watson coefficient = 1.652 is in the range of 1.5 - 2.5, so there is no first-order chain autocorrelation phenomenon.

Table 8 ANOVA test results of the regression model

ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	133.867	5	26.773	100.204	0.000 ^b
	Residual	105.539	395	0.267		
	Total	239.407	400			
a. Dependent Variable: Study and living habits						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Perceptions and Learning Methods, Technology, Family and Society, Environment and Friends, Lecturers						

(Source: SPSS data running results)

- Test sig F = 000b < 0.05 so the multiple linear regression model is consistent with the dataset and can be used.

Table 9 Regression coefficients of independent variables

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-0.154	0.217		-0.708	0.479		
	Perceptions and Methods	0.477	0.053	0.471	9.059	0.000	0.413	2.421
	Technology	0.247	0.040	0.215	6.135	0.000	0.907	1.102
	Lecturer	0.143	0.042	0.130	3.408	0.001	0.772	1.296
	Environment and friends	-0.119	0.051	-0.104	-2.346	0.019	0.563	1.777
	Family and Society	0.232	0.058	0.215	3.985	0.000	0.382	2.618

a. Dependent Variable: Study and living habits

(Source: SPSS data running results)

- Sig tests that the regression coefficients of the independent variables NTPP, CN, GV, MTBB, and GDSH are all less than 0.05, so these independent variables are all meaningful to explain the dependent variable, not excluded from the model.
- The VIF coefficients of independent variables are all less than 3, so no multi-collinear phenomenon occurs.
- The regression coefficients of the NTPP, CN, GV and GDSH variables are all greater than 0, so these variables when included in the regression analysis all act in the same direction as the Chinese dependent variable. Based on the magnitude of the Beta normalized regression coefficient, the order of impact from strongest to weakest of independent variables to dependent variables is: NTPP (0.477) > CN (0.247) > Social Education (0.232) > GV (0.143). And the MTBB variable has a regression coefficient = -0.119 < 0, so this variable, when included in the regression analysis, will have the opposite effect on the Chinese dependent variable.

Corresponds to:

- + Transforming Awareness and methods have the first strong influence on the living and learning habits of students of the School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry.
- + Turning technology has the second strongest impact on the living and learning habits of students of the School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry.
- + The third strongest influence on the living and learning habits of students of the School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry.
- + The fourth strongest influence on the living and learning habits of students of the School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry.
- + And finally, the environment and friends have the weakest influence on the living and learning habits of students of the School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry.

(Source: SPSS data running results)

Figure 2 Normalized Residual Frequency Chart Histogram

- The mean value of MEAN = 1.96E- 15 is close to 0, the standard deviation is 0.994 which is close to 1. Thus, it can be said that the distribution of the surplus is approximately standard. Therefore, it can be concluded that: The assumption of the standard distribution of the remainder is not violated. The regression model used is statistically relevant.

(Source: SPSS data running results)

Figure 3 Normal P-P Plot Normalized Residual Chart

For the Normal P-P Plot chart, we also see that the data points in the distribution of the remainder are close to the diagonal, thus, assuming that the standard distribution of the remainder is not violated.

(Source: SPSS data running results)

Figure 4 Normalized Residual Chart

- The normalized residuals are distributed around the 0-degree diaphragm, so the assumption of a linear relationship is not violated.

Thus, with the 7 hypotheses initially set out in the research hypothesis section, there are 5 accepted hypotheses corresponding to the following variables: Cognition and method (NTPP); Technology (CN); Family and Society (Social Education); Lecturers (Teachers) and Environment and Friends (MTBB). =>

Normalized regression equations:

$$TQ = 0.477x \text{ NTPP} + 0.247x \text{ CN} + 0.232 x \text{ GDXH} + 0.143 x \text{ GV} - 0.119 x \text{ MTBB}.$$

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of data analysis from 401 valid survey forms of students of the School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry, the study identified and evaluated the factors affecting the living and learning habits of the Gen Z generation. Pearson correlation analysis and multiple linear regression analysis, the constructed scale is highly reliable (Cronbach's Alpha > 0.6) and clear statistical significance (Sig. F < 0.05). The results of the study shed light on 5 main factors affecting living and learning habits, including: Cognition and learning methods, Technology, Family and Society, Lecturers, and Environment and friends. These factors explain 55.4% of changes in lifestyle-learning habits according to the regression model.

- Cognition and learning methods: This is the factor with the strongest impact on living and learning habits, with a normalization coefficient of $\beta = 0.477$ (Sig. = 0.000 < 0.05), indicating a favorable effect. This result emphasizes that personal awareness of the importance of learning and effective learning methods is a core factor in the formation of positive habits of students. This is consistent with previous studies on the role of individual cognition in learning behavior.
- Technology: This factor has a positive effect with a normalization coefficient of $\beta = 0.247$ (Sig. = 0.000 < 0.05), ranking second in terms of impact. Technology assists students in accessing materials and managing learning, but excessive use can also disrupt healthy living habits, such as insomnia or reduced social interaction. This result is similar to studies on the dual impact of technology on Gen Z.
- Family and society: With a normalized coefficient of $\beta = 0.232$ (Sig. = 0.000 < 0.05), this factor shows that support from family and social expectations play an important role in promoting study habits and disciplined activities. The results are consistent with the view that the home environment is fundamental to influencing student behavior, especially in the context of Vietnamese culture.
- Lecturers: This factor has a positive effect on the normalization coefficient $\beta = 0.143$ (Sig. = 0.001 < 0.05), indicating that teaching methods, support and feedback from lecturers contribute to shaping students' learning habits. Although the level of influence is not too great, the role of lecturers still has practical significance in the higher education environment.

- Environment and friends: This is the only factor that has the opposite effect, with a normalization coefficient of $\beta = -0.119$ (Sig. = 0.019 < 0.05). This result indicates that the peer environment, if not well controlled, can be distracting or reduce students' academic discipline. This reflects the fact that friends are both a source of emotional support and can be a hindrance depending on the level of engagement.

4.1. Recommendations

- Recommendations for Students

Students are the central object of the study, and with an active role in the formation of study and living habits, the authors make specific recommendations as follows:

- Raising awareness and developing learning methods:

The "Perception and learning methods" factor had the strongest impact ($\beta = 0.477$), indicating that this is the core factor that needs to be focused. Students need to be well aware of the importance of maintaining a regular study routine and developing a specific study plan. To do this, students should participate in seminars, short courses or training programs on time management skills, effective memorization methods (such as the Pomodoro method, mind maps) organized by the school or educational institutions. For example, students can apply the Pomodoro technique (25 minutes of study, 5 minutes of rest) to enhance concentration and avoid burnout. In addition, self-assessment and adjustment of weekly study habits also help students recognize weaknesses and gradually improve their academic performance.

- Manage and utilize technology effectively:

Technology was a significant positive factor ($\beta = 0.247$), but the survey data also showed that excessive use of technology (e.g., using phones at night, social media) disrupted healthy living habits. Students need to set a limit on the time spent using electronic devices, such as not using a phone after 10 p.m., to ensure 7-8 hours of sleep a day, thereby maintaining health and concentration. At the same time, students should take advantage of learning support apps such as "Notion" to manage notes, "Google Calendar" to schedule studies, or "Forest" to maintain focus by "planting virtual trees" during class. These tools not only help increase learning efficiency but also minimize distractions from entertainment platforms.

- Control and take advantage of the friend environment:

The environment and friends have the opposite impact ($\beta = -0.119$), indicating that this is a potential risk factor for distraction if not managed well. Students need to actively select friends with positive study habits to motivate and support each other. For example, joining study groups or academic clubs on campus can help students build an active community of friends where they can share materials, discuss assignments, and make progress together. On the contrary, students should limit participating in prolonged recreational activities (such as playing games, gathering excessively) with friends who have undisciplined study habits, to avoid negatively affecting their study time.

- Build personal discipline and healthy living habits:

The survey results show that 17.7% of students study less than 1 hour a day, which can affect academic performance if not improved. Students need to make a reasonable time spending plan, balancing study, rest and entertainment. One suggestion is to apply the 80/20 rule: spend 80% of your time studying and personal development, 20% for entertainment and relaxation. Time management apps like "Trello" (managing tasks by list) or "Todoist" (making to-do lists) can assist students in tracking their academic progress and maintaining regular routines. In addition, students should focus on taking care of their health by eating healthy, exercising at least 30 minutes a day, and getting enough sleep to ensure energy for studying.

- Recommendations for schools, families and society

External factors such as school, family, and society play an important role in supporting students to form positive habits. Here are the detailed recommendations:

- For schools

- Strengthening the role of lecturers: With an impact level of $\beta = 0.143$, lecturers need support to improve teaching efficiency and interaction with students. Schools should provide regular training sessions for faculty on innovative teaching methods (e.g., project-based learning, group discussions) and constructive feedback skills. For example, instructors can use online tools like "Kahoot" to create fun quick tests, or host individual counseling sessions to help students adjust their study habits.

- Improvement of facilities and learning environment: Survey data shows that clean and comfortable learning facilities and environment are positively evaluated (Mean = 3.33). The university needs to continue to invest in a library system with abundant resources, expand quiet learning spaces and equip modern equipment such as computers and high-speed wifi. In addition, organizing periodic cleaning sessions or the campaign "Maintaining a green - clean - beautiful learning environment" can encourage students to be more aware of their learning space.

- Integrate soft skills education: Schools should include soft skills training programs (time management, teamwork, effective use of technology) in the main or extracurricular program. For example, organizing workshops on "How to Plan Effectively Learning" or "Using Technology to Optimize Learning" will help students improve their awareness and learning methods.

- For families

- Support and motivate children: The family has a positive impact ($\beta = 0.232$), which is an important source of emotional and material support. Parents should regularly chat with their children to grasp the learning situation, share time management experiences and encourage their children to build disciplined study habits. For example, parents can work with their children to create a weekly schedule, set specific learning goals (such as completing 2 chapters of books per week) and reward them when they achieve them.

- Monitor and orient technology use: Parents need to monitor their children's technology use habits, especially at night, to avoid affecting health and learning. They can encourage their children to use learning apps instead of social networks, and participate in technology talks organized by the school to better understand how to support them.

- Create a learning environment at home: Families should provide a quiet, well-lit and noise-limited learning space, and make sure their children have all the necessary learning materials. This helps reinforce students' self-study habits even at home.

- For society

- Build active learning communities: Mass organizations, clubs, or online communities (such as Facebook and Zalo study groups) should create forums for students to exchange, share learning experiences, and support each other. For example, organizing academic competitions or online discussions about effective learning methods can encourage students to participate and develop positive habits.

- Propagation of healthy habits: Society needs to promote communication campaigns about the importance of healthy learning and living habits, such as through short videos on TikTok, Instagram – platforms that are popular with Gen Z. Content can focus on balancing learning and entertainment, or how to use technology responsibly.

- **Recommendations for management agencies and educational organizations**

In order to create more favorable conditions for Gen Z students to develop active learning and living habits, management agencies and educational institutions need to take specific actions:

- Enhance education on technology and study habits

The Ministry of Education and Training and local management agencies should coordinate with schools to develop propaganda programs about the benefits and risks of technology in learning. Workshops or guidance materials on "Using Technology for Effective Learning" can be widely released, emphasizing how to leverage technology without compromising health. For example, organize campaigns such as the "7-Day No Phone Challenge after 10 p.m." to encourage students to change their habits.

- Develop learning tools and products:

Educational institutions should partner with tech businesses to develop student-friendly learning apps, such as e-learning platforms that integrate time management, or AI apps that help personalize learning plans. These tools need to be designed to be simple, easy to use, and fit into Gen Z's habits, thereby competing with distractions such as social media or gaming. In addition, making these tools free or at a low cost will encourage students to use them more widely.

- Control the environment around the school:

Local authorities, especially in areas with a large number of students such as around Hanoi University of Industry, need to strengthen the management of negative entertainment activities (such as internet cafes, bars) that can distract students. Measures such as periodic check-ups, propaganda about the harms of an undisciplined lifestyle, or organizing community events (sports festivals, book fairs) will help orient students to useful activities, thereby minimizing the negative impact of the peer environment.

- Policy support for life skills education:

State management agencies should enact policies to encourage universities to integrate life skills education into their curricula, with a focus on time management, self-study, and the use of technology. For example, it is possible to implement the "Self-Reliant Gen Z Students" program with free courses on study habits, funded by the state budget or social organizations. This not only raises students' awareness but also creates conditions for them to apply their knowledge in practice.

The above recommendations are built based on research results, aiming to optimize positive factors (cognition, technology, family, lecturers) and minimize negative impacts from the environment of friends, thereby helping Gen Z students at the School of Economics - Hanoi University of Industry develop sustainable and effective living and learning habits.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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